

Design of Efficient Adder Circuits Using PROPOSED PARITY PRESERVING GATE (PPPG)

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ABSTRACT

Reversible logic is becoming an important research area which aims mainly to reduce power dissipation during computing. In this paper we introduce a new parity preserving reversible gate PPPG (a 5x5 gate). This gate is universal in the sense it can synthesize any arbitrary Boolean function. It is also a parity preserving gate in which the parity of input matches the parity of the output. This parity preserving gate allows any single fault to be detected at the circuit's primary outputs. By using one PPPG a fault tolerant reversible full adder circuit can be realized. The proposed fault tolerant full adder (PFTFA) is used to design other arithmetic logic circuits for which it is used as the fundamental building block. The PFTFA gate is also used to implement high speed adders which are efficient basic building blocks of logic circuits. It has also been demonstrated that the proposed high speed adders are efficient in terms of gate count, garbage outputs and constant inputs than the existing counterparts.

KEYWORDS

Reversible logic, Garbage output, Reversible gate, Proposed Parity Preserving Gate, Constant inputs and Proposed fault tolerant full adder, Carry Skip Adder, Carry Look Ahead Adder, Ripple carry Adder

1. INTRODUCTION

Today's computing world is in the quench of ultra low power dissipation. With the advancement of technology, complex systems are obtained with high clock frequency for a greater speed and an increase in packing the transistors on a chip which results more power consumption. All the logical operations performed by millions of gates in a conventional computer are irreversible. That is, whenever a logical operation is performed information about the input is erased or lost and is dissipated in heat. An irreversible logic computation generates $kT \ln 2$ joules of heat energy for each bit of information lost, where k is Boltzmann's constant and T the absolute temperature at which computation is performed [14], which was proved by Researchers like Landauer. When a computation is performed in a reversible way [2], Bennett showed that $kT \ln 2$ energy dissipation would not occur, as there is a direct relationship between the amount of energy dissipated in a system and the number of bits erased during computation. Circuits that do not lose information are said to be Reversible.

Only when the system comprises of reversible gates, reversible computation in a system can be achieved. Reversible circuits can produce unique output for distinct input combination, and vice versa. In the reversible circuits, there is a one-to-one mapping between input and output vectors.

Bennett's theorem [2] about heat dissipation is only a necessary but not sufficient condition, but its extreme importance lies in the fact that every future technology will have to use reversible gates to reduce power. For every 18 months the processing power doubles according to Moore's law. The present irreversible technologies dissipate a lot of heat which reduces the life of the circuit. Information is not erased in reversible logic operations which in turn dissipates very less heat. In future the reversible logic will be the prominent technology in the field of low power high performance circuits.

Synthesis of reversible logic circuits differs from the combinational circuits in many ways [10]. In Reversible circuit each output cannot be used more than once, it means there should be no fan-out and for each unique output pattern there should be a input pattern. Finally, the resulting circuit must be acyclic which means the output should feed not more than one input. Any reversible gate performs the permutation of its input patterns only and realizes the functions that are reversible. If a reversible gate has k inputs, and therefore k outputs, then it is a $k \times k$ reversible gate. Any reversible circuit design includes only the gates that are reversible. In a reversible circuit, the outputs that are not used as primary outputs or as an input to the other gate are called as garbage outputs. The input lines that are set to constants are termed as constant inputs. An efficient design should keep the number of garbage outputs and constant inputs to minimum.

Fault tolerance is the property that enables a system to continue operating properly in the event of the failure of some its components. The detection and correction of faults become easier and simple when the system is incorporated with fault tolerant components. Fault tolerance is obtained by parity in communication and many other systems. So the development of fault tolerant reversible systems in nanotechnology is motivated by parity preserving reversible circuits. A gating network is said to be parity preserving when its individual gate is parity preserving [18]. So, parity preserving reversible circuits require parity preserving reversible logic gates to construct.

A new 5×5 Parity Preserving Logic Gate, PPPG is proposed. PPPG is a parity preserving gate, that is, the parity of the outputs matches the parity of the inputs. PPPG is universal in the sense that it can be used to synthesize any arbitrary Boolean function. By using only one PPPG a fault tolerant reversible full adder circuit can be realized. The presented design does not produce any unnecessary garbage outputs. Minimizing the number of garbage outputs are the major concern in reversible logic design [10]. The presented PFTFA block can be used to realize other fault tolerant arithmetic logic circuits in nanotechnology such as ripple carry adder, carry look-ahead adder and carry-skip adder.

1.1 Reversible Logic Gates

1.1.1. Basic Reversible Gates

A gate where inputs can be recovered from its outputs is called a reversible gate. A reversible gate involves bijective function having k inputs and k outputs. So far many reversible gates are implemented. Among them 2×2 Feynman gate [18] (shown in Figure 1a), 3×3 Fredkin gate [18] (shown in Figure 1d), 3×3 Toffoli gate [18] (shown in Figure 1c) and 3×3 Peres gate [18] (shown in Figure 1b) are the most referred. Some of the gates are one-through gates which are Feynman (FG), Fredkin (FRG) and Peres (PG) gates, that is, one of the input line is identical to one of the output line. Some gates are two-through like Toffoli gate, that is, two of its inputs are identical to two of its outputs. The sufficient conditions for a gate to become reversible are an equal number of input and output lines and for every unique output combination there should be unique input combination.

Figure 1a. Feynman gate Figure 1b. Peres gate Figure 1c. Toffoli gate Figure 1d. Fredkin gate

1.1.2. Parity Preserving Reversible Gates

A reversible gate is called parity preserving reversible gate if its input parity matches the parity of its output. The parity preserving of a reversible logic gate can be defined as the EX-OR of the all inputs should be equal to the EX-OR of the all outputs. A few parity preserving logic gates have been presented in the paper. Among them 3*3 Feynman Double gate (F2G) [18] depicted in Figure 2a and 3*3 Fredkin gate (FRG) [18] depicted in Figure 2b are one through gates, which means one of the inputs is also output. Recently a new 3*3 parity preserving reversible gate, namely New Fault Tolerant gate (NFT) [18] depicted in Figure 2c, a 4*4 parity preserving HC gate (PPHCG) [18] depicted in Figure 2d and a 4*4 parity preserving IG gate [18] depicted in Figure 2e have been proposed.

Figure 2a. F2G Figure 2b. FRG Figure 2c. NFT gate Figure 2d. PPHCG gate Figure 2e. IG gate

1.1.3. A New 5x5 Parity Preserving Reversible Gate

This paper presents a new 5x5 parity preserving reversible gate, PPPG, depicted in Figure 3a. When one of the input variables is also output then the gate is called one-through. This gate is an one-through gate. The truth table of the gate is shown in Table 1. The input pattern corresponding to particular output pattern is uniquely determined from the truth table. The proposed reversible PPPG is parity preserving. This is readily verified by comparing the parity of the input to the parity of the output that is $A \oplus B \oplus C \oplus D \oplus E$ and $P \oplus Q \oplus R \oplus S \oplus T$. The newly proposed PPPG gate is universal in the sense that it can be used for implementing any arbitrary Boolean functions.

Figure 3a. PPPG gate

Figure 3b. PPPG as AND and XOR

Figure 3c PPPG as NOT and OR

Table 1. Truth Table of the Parity Preserving Proposed Gate

A	B	C	D	E		P	Q	R	S	T
0	0	0	0	0		0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	1		0	0	0	0	1
0	0	0	1	0		0	0	1	0	0
0	0	0	1	1		0	0	1	0	1
0	0	1	0	0		0	1	1	1	0
0	0	1	0	1		0	1	1	1	1
0	0	1	1	0		0	1	0	0	1
0	0	1	1	1		0	1	0	0	0
0	1	0	0	0		0	1	1	0	1
0	1	0	0	1		0	1	1	0	0
0	1	0	1	0		0	1	0	1	0
0	1	0	1	1		0	1	0	1	1
0	1	1	0	0		0	0	0	1	1
0	1	1	0	1		0	0	0	1	0
0	1	1	1	0		0	0	1	1	1
0	1	1	1	1		0	0	1	1	0
1	0	0	0	0		1	1	1	0	0
1	0	0	0	1		1	1	1	0	1
1	0	0	1	0		1	1	0	1	1
1	0	0	1	1		1	1	0	1	0
1	0	1	0	0		1	1	1	1	0
1	0	1	0	1		1	1	1	1	1
1	0	1	1	0		1	1	0	0	1
1	0	1	1	1		1	1	0	0	0
1	1	0	0	0		1	0	0	1	0
1	1	0	0	1		1	0	0	1	1
1	1	0	1	0		1	0	1	1	0
1	1	0	1	1		1	0	1	1	1
1	1	1	0	0		1	0	0	0	0
1	1	1	0	1		1	0	0	0	1
1	1	1	1	0		1	0	1	0	0
1	1	1	1	1		1	0	1	0	1

1.2. Fault Tolerant Reversible Full Adder Circuit

Reversible logic implementation of full adder circuit has been studied by several authors in the literature [10-18]. With at least one constant input and two garbage outputs a reversible full adder circuit can be realized. This requirement is not the same for fault tolerant reversible full adder circuit. Because in a fault tolerant full adder circuit the input parity must match the parity of the outputs. This section first establishes the minimum number of garbage outputs and constant inputs required to design a fault tolerant reversible full adder circuit and then proposes a new realization of fault tolerant reversible full adder circuit using the newly proposed PPPG gate.

Theorem 1: Any realization of a fault tolerant reversible full adder circuit needs at least three garbage outputs and two constant inputs.

Proof: The full adder circuit output equations $S=A \oplus B \oplus C_{in}$ and $C_{out}=(A \oplus B)C_{in} \oplus AB$ produce the same output $S=1$ and $C_{out}=0$, for the three distinct input combinations $A=0, B=0, C_{in}=1$; $A=0, B=1, C_{in}=0$ and $A=1, B=0, C_{in}=0$. The parity of the input vector matches the parity of the corresponding output vector. To separate all repeated values of outputs S and C_{out} as well as keeping their parity unchanged, at least three garbage outputs are required. Thus the total number of outputs is $2+3=5$. Now since in a reversible circuit the number of inputs must be equal to the number of outputs and there are three inputs in a full adder circuit A, B and C_{in} , the other two inputs need to be constant inputs.

There are three fault tolerant reversible full adder circuits in the literature [3][10][11][18]. The fault tolerant full adder circuit in [6] requires six parity preserving reversible gates (two FRGs and four F2Gs) and the fault tolerant full adder circuit in [3] uses four FRGs. This paper presents a new design of fault tolerant reversible full adder circuit namely “Proposed Fault Tolerant Full Adder (PFTFA)” that uses only one PPPG, depicted in Figure 4. It requires only one clock cycle.

Figure 4. Fault tolerant reversible full adder using PPPG

2. APPLICATIONS OF THE PROPOSED GATE (PG)

To illustrate the applications of the proposed gate, two types of adders – ripple carry, carry look-ahead adder and carry skip adders are designed. The adders implemented using the Proposed Gate are most optimized in terms of reversible gates compared to their existing counter parts.

2.1. Ripple Carry Adder

The ripple carry adder is implemented using full adder as the basic building block. The fault tolerant reversible ripple carry adder is obtained by cascading a series of fault tolerant reversible full adders as shown in figure 5.

Figure 5. Ripple Carry Adder Using The PFTFA

The output expressions for a ripple carry adder are:

$$S_i = A \oplus B \oplus C_{in}; \quad C_{out} = (A \oplus B)C_{in} \oplus AB;$$

It can be inferred, from the Fig. 6 that for N bit addition, the proposed ripple carry adder architecture uses only N reversible gates and produces only 3N garbage outputs. But, the ripple carry adder using our proposed gate (PG) is the most optimized one. Table III shows the result that compares the proposed ripple carry adder using PG gate, with the existing full adders of. It is observed that the proposed circuit is better than the existing circuits; both in terms of reversible gates and garbage outputs.

2.2. Carry Look-Ahead Adder

By reducing the time required to produce the carry fast adders can be designed. One way of computing is, the input carry of stage i can be obtained from all the carry signals of preceding stages like i-1, i-2, ..., 0, than waiting for a carry to pass slowly from one stage to another stage. Carry look-ahead adders use the above principle. By using parallel carry computations high speed can be achieved in Carry look-ahead adders (CLA) compared to other adders. Generation or Propagation of a carry is determined by the bit pair, in the binary sequence to be added, from CLA logic. Carry ahead of time is determined by the pre-process of the two numbers being added. The ripple carry effect is eliminated when the actual addition is performed.

The adder is based on the fact that a carry signal will be generated in two cases:

1. When both bits A_i and B_i are 1, or
2. When one of the two bits is 1 and the carry-in is 1.

Thus,

$$C_{out} = C_{i+1} = A_i \cdot B_i + (A_i \oplus B_i) \cdot C_i$$

The above expression can also be represented as:

$$C_{i+1} = G_i + P_i \cdot C_i.$$

$$\text{Where, } G_i = A_i \cdot B_i \text{ and } P_i = A_i \oplus B_i$$

Applying this to a 4-bit adder:

$$(1) C_1 = G_0 + P_0 C_0$$

$$(2) C_2 = G_1 + P_1 C_1$$

$$= G_1 + P_1 G_0 + P_1 P_0 C_0$$

$$(3) C_3 = G_2 + P_2 C_2$$

$$= G_2 + P_2 G_1 + P_2 P_1 G_0 + P_2 P_1 P_0 C_0$$

$$(4) C_4 = G_3 + P_3 C_3 = G_3 + P_3 G_2 + P_3 P_2 G_1 + P_3 P_2 P_1 G_0 + P_3 P_2 P_1 P_0 C_0$$

The Sum signal can be calculated as follows:

$$S_i = A_i \oplus B_i \oplus C_i = P_i \oplus C_i$$

The CLA can be broken up into two modules:

1. Proposed Gate as Full Adder (PFA): This generates G_i , P_i , and S_i .
2. Carry Look-Ahead Logic: The CLA generates the carry-out bits

Figure 6. Carry look Ahead adder using PPPG

2.3. Carry Skip Adder

The carry-propagation delay is reduced using carry skip adder by skipping some consecutive adder stages. The carry-skip adder consumes less power and requires less chip area compared to the carry look-ahead adder, but comparable in speed. The addition of two binary digits at stage i , of the ripple carry adder depends on the carry in, C_i , which in reality is the carry out, C_{i-1} , of the previous stage. The carryout of the previous stage is directly given to the carry-in of the next stage. Therefore, in order to calculate the sum and the carry out, C_{i+1} , of stage i , it is imperative that the carry in, C_i , be known in advance. It is interesting to note that in some cases C_{i+1} can be calculated without knowledge of C_i . Boolean Equations of a Full Adder

$$P_i = A_i \oplus B_i \quad \text{---- carry propagate of } i\text{th stage}$$

$$S_i = P_i \oplus C_i \quad \text{---- sum of } i\text{th stage}$$

$$C_{i+1} = A_i B_i + P_i C_i \quad \text{-----carry out of } i\text{th stage}$$

Supposing that $A_i = B_i$, then P_i would become zero. This would make C_{i+1} to depend only on the inputs A_i and B_i , without needing to know the value of C_i .

$$\text{If } A_i = B_i = 0 \text{ then } C_{i+1} = A_i B_i = 0 \quad \text{If } A_i = B_i = 1 \text{ then } C_{i+1} = A_i B_i = 1$$

Hence carry out can be computed at any stage of the addition. These findings would enable us to build an adder whose average time of computation would be proportional to the longest chains of zeros and of different digits of A and B .

If A and B are different digits then next stage carry will be previous stage only. If both the inputs are different then P_i will be one. Then the generate term will be zero but P_i is one. So previous stage carry will be propagated to next stage.

If $A_i B_i$ is 'one' then C_{i+1} will become C_i .

When two bits of opposite value is compared, the carry out will be equivalent to the carry in of the respective stage. Hence simply the carry can be propagated to the next stage without having to wait for the sum to be calculated.

Figure 7. carry skip adder using PPPG

3. RESULTS

Table 2 Comparative Experimental Results of Different Fault Tolerant 1-Bit Full Adder Circuits

Design	No. of Reversible Gates	Constant inputs	Garbage outputs
Proposed Circuit	1	2	3
1-bit FTFA [18]	2	2	3
1-bit FTFA[10][11]	2	2	3
1-bit FTFA [3]	4	2	3

Table 3 Comparative Experimental Results of Different Fault Tolerant 4-Bit Ripple Carry Adder Circuits

Design	No. of Reversible Gates	Constant inputs	Garbage outputs
4-bit RCA using Proposed Gate	4	8	12
4-bit RCA[18]	8	8	12
4-bit RCA[10][11]	8	8	12
4-bit RCA[3]	8	8	12

Table 4 Comparative Experimental Results of Different Fault Tolerant 4-Bit Carry Skip Adder Circuits

Design	No. of Reversible Gates	Constant inputs	Garbage outputs
4-bit CSA using Proposed Gate	4 PFTFA + 4 NFT + 2 F2G=10	15	19
4-bit CSA[18]	8 MIG + 4 NFT + 2 F2G=14	15	19
4-bit CSA[3]	20 FRG	11	16

Table 5 Comparative Experimental Results of Different Fault Tolerant 2-Bit Carry Look Ahead Adder Circuits

Design	No. of Reversible Gates	Constant inputs	Garbage outputs
2-bit CLA using Proposed Gate	2 PFTFA + 5 NFT + 10 F2G=17	26	28
2-bit CLA[18]	4 MIG + 5 NFT + 10 F2G=19	26	28

4. CONCLUSION

The main aim of this paper is the proposal of a new 5x5 parity preserving reversible gate called PPPG gate and demonstrates its universality by realizing all possible Boolean functions. The proposed gate is being used to design optimized architectures of fault tolerant reversible ripple carry adder, carry look ahead adder and carry skip adder. It is proved that the adder architectures using the proposed gate are better than the existing counterparts in literature, in terms of number of reversible gates and garbage outputs. All the proposed architectures are analysed in terms of technology independent implementations. In low power CMOS, nanotechnology, and quantum computing reversible logic is widely used. The proposed parity preserving reversible gate (PPPG) and efficient fault tolerant adder architectures are one of the contributions to reversible logic. The proposed circuits can be used to design large reversible systems. In a nutshell, the advent of reversible logic will significantly contribute in reducing the power consumption.

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